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Digital Life and Business Transformation of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State of Nigeria

Chukwuemeka, Blessing Chinwe^{1*} and Prof. N. M. Ile²^{1,2}Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu***Corresponding Author****Background**

The global oil and gas sector is witnessing a change like never before. Challenges faced by the oil and gas industry in 2020 called for a worldwide change. According to Gartner's research, the oil and gas sector must build on optimizing business performance to create new capabilities. And for these two, the business models need a solid digital foundation. The oil and gas sector leaders are automating the oil and gas operations using artificial intelligence and machine learning. The digital strategy is focused on reducing costs and increasing the sector's efficiency (Birlasoft, 2022).

Today, a lot of people are surprised to learn that, even though they do not participate on social media and only use their computers for work or some other activities, they have a digital life. This is partly because generally -available information about you is gotten from the internet, and this

information is used by firms or organizations to create records about you (Barker, 2016). Digital life is life itself, and technology has now become an essential part of being what it means to be human. More people in the world have access to a smartphone than they do running water, which is a phenomenal reality. Regardless of whether or not you own a device yourself, mobile technology has become all-pervasive. Digitization fuels global healthcare services and research facilities, powers utility infrastructure, supports education systems, revolution how we run businesses and, at a more intrinsic level, enables the human race to communicate across borders. The enormous benefit technology has brought to the world in such a short space of time is incredible. Never before have we seen such progress unilaterally sweep the world and affect such change. That is why the possibilities of technology should be open to everyone (Álvarez-Pallete, 2022).

There is also a more fundamental economic impact achieved from digital technology that we simply cannot ignore. The application of digital technology now contributes as much as 10% to total GDP in the world's more digitally

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the digital life and business transformation of gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between e-safety and customer experience, as well as ascertain the relationship between effective communication and employee experience of gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The research utilized a descriptive survey design. The study's population consisted of three thousand three hundred and eighty-six (3,386) staff from selected oil firms. Simple random sampling was employed to select the sample unit, resulting in a sample size of 345 using Ferund Williams's formula. A total of 295 staff members returned accurately filled questionnaires, yielding a 94 percent response rate. Data were presented and analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation through a Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were examined using Pearson correlation (r). The findings indicated a significant positive relationship between e-safety and customer experience, $r(95, n = 295) = .610 < .983, p < .05$. Additionally, there was a significant relationship between communication and employee experience of gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, $r(95, n = 295) = .411 < .846, p < .05$. The study concluded that both e-safety and communication exhibited a positive and significant relationship with customer experience and employee experience of gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Among other recommendations, the study suggested that gasoline firms' management should prioritize online safety to safeguard individuals, themselves, and others from potential online risks that could jeopardize personal information.

Keywords: Digital life; Transformation; Gasoline firms; Customer Experience, E-safety Employee; River State

developed countries. This is proof of the enormous power and potential of the digital revolution we are living in. Needless to say, this contribution is projected to rise significantly over the next few years, across all corners of the globe. However, to ensure that opportunity is fully exploited for the benefit of world economies and the lives of global citizens, it is our firm view that governments, economists, policy makers and those involved in the development of digital innovation need a more sophisticated indicator of the relative success of the digital economy. Without this, there is no goalpost at which we can all aim and no clear guidance on where we should be prioritizing investment (Álvarez-Pallete, 2022).

The openness of operating systems, digital skills, confidence, laws, and the ability to innovate, all contribute to the value of digital life and, in turn, the strength of a digital economy. The Index has highlighted that while the US and European countries display great strength in many areas, Latin American countries rank particularly highly for entrepreneurship. In fact, Colombia and Chile fall in the top eight performing countries relative to GDP per capita, outperforming those countries perceived to be more digitally developed. By now, we are all aware that our lives are becoming increasingly digital; we bank via apps, share updates via social and make countless purchases online. Digitalization becomes pertinent as it will drive operational improvements, which will lead to better results. Digital transformation covers a huge number of processes, interactions, transactions, technological evolutions, changes, internal and external factors, industries, stakeholders and so forth (Birlasoft, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

A generation ago, Information Technology and digital media were niche skills. Today, they are a core competency necessary to succeed in most careers. That is why digital skills are an essential part of a comprehensive education framework. Without a national digital education programme, command of and access to technology will be distributed unevenly, exacerbating inequality and hindering socio-economic mobility. Digital connectivity has the power to change the world and make a powerful impact on the life of millions of people. The corona virus outbreak gave rise to an outbreak of digitalization across various industries and empowered multiple businesses to set a global presence, create unparalleled value, and capture opportunities. The Oil and Gas sector has played a crucial part in the world's economic transformation. The industry needs digital transformation now more than ever. The oil and gas companies could not identify and focus on the business's priorities. The gasoline firms could not understand the dynamics and requirements of the markets and the customers. Also, they were unsure about the financial returns on digital investments. This made top executives reluctant to invest in big digital projects. This can be addressed via using the right technology. This has led to poor customer and employee experience.

As a result of these problems, if not tackled will reduced commitment to create a digital life that is accessible for all. Digital technologies have the power to invigorate social economic development and support stable and long-term economic growth. Based on this, the study aimed to examine the Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between effective communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Research Question

The following Research question guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between effective communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses guided the study

- i. There is no significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significance relationship between effective communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The society at large stands to benefit from the study as business transformation could engage daily in a job and as a result, reduce some social vices and other criminal activities, which result from unemployment and idleness. Lastly, the work will be of immense benefit to scholars and researchers because, it will stimulate further research in the area. The openness of operating systems, digital skills, confidence, laws, and the ability to innovate, all contribute to the value of digital life and, in turn, the strength of a digital economy.

Scope of the Study

The study will focus on Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The key management issues include: e-safety and customer experience, communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Digital

Digital describes electronic technology that generates, stores, and processes data. It is tempting to look for simple definitions, but to be meaningful and sustainable; we believe that digital should be seen less as a thing and more as a way of *doing* things. To help make this definition more concrete, we have broken it down into three attributes: creating value at the new frontiers of the business world, creating value in the processes that execute a vision of customer experiences, and building foundational capabilities that support the entire structure, (Dörner & Edelman, 2015). Being digital is about using data to make better and faster decisions, devolving decision making to smaller teams, and developing much more iterative and rapid ways of doing things.

Life

Life is the condition that distinguishes animals and plants from inorganic matter, including the capacity for growth, reproduction, functional activity, and continual change preceding death. Life is a quality that distinguishes matter that has biological processes, such as signaling and self-sustaining processes, from matter that does not, and is defined by the capacity for growth, reaction to stimuli, metabolism, energy transformation, and reproduction, (Merriam-Webster Dictionary 2022).

Digital Life

The term “digital life” stands for a way of life in which digital technologies are an indispensable part of life. In its contrasting use, the term “digital life” is used to distinguish between the parts of human life that take place in “cyberspace”, or which are closely related to digital technologies, and the other areas of life that take place in “real life” and independently of the use of digital technologies, (Lengsfeld,2022). “Digital technology is so broad today as to encompass almost everything. No product is made today, no person moves today, nothing is collected, analyzed or communicated without some ‘digital technology’ being an integral part of it (Rossetto, 2018).

Within the last few decades, the impacts of digital life have changed significantly. It is barely possible to imagine what daily life would look like without all those used gadgets. A big proportion of people are doing their work mainly on a computer, everyone is checking their mobile phones a lot of times every day. Online activities can affect truth and trust of people, through conversations on Facebook, etc. Moreover, the well-being of individuals can be

influenced, physically as well as emotionally. The impact of digital life on society brings exceptional benefits in many different fields. The healthcare industry benefits, whether it comes to the control of a pregnancy or the access to information. Along with such benefits are negative impacts in a different way (Meyer 2018). The development of digital life brings several negative impacts with it. All the information can cause inattentive behavior, which affects the personal life in many aspects, whether it is studies or friendship. A negative result of our digital life is the information overload (Meyer 2018).

Components of Digital Life that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Shibley (2004) maintained that the Components of Digital Life include: Internet connectivity, Digital media consumption, Digital media creation, home control and automation, Integrated communications. The eight components of digital life include creativity, critical thinking and evaluation, cultural and social understanding, collaboration, find and select information, effective communication, e-safety, and functional skills (Shively, 2017; Hague & Payton, 2010).

E – Safety

E-safety is often defined as the safe and responsible use of technology. This includes the use of the internet and also other means of communication using electronic media (e.g. text messages, gaming devices, email etc.). In practice, e-safety is as much about behaviour as it is electronic security. E-safety may also be referred to as internet safety, online safety, cyber safety or web safety. To simply explain E-Safety, it means being safe on the internet. Some people may even include the safe use of technology in e-safety. It may also be used to refer to the action of protecting individuals from harmful content online, such as – adult content, grooming and cyberbullying. Internet has reached every corner of the world that can be accessed by different kinds of people. As we do not know their intention, free interaction can sometimes bring about cyberbullying and harassment (Wilshire, 2023).

Effective Communications

Like any industry, communication is key to an effective workplace. But industries with several safety hazards must prioritize engagement to avoid mishaps. Without quality communication, workers will not understand their role on the job site. This can lead to mismanaged projects and a decrease in productivity. However, effective communication outlines clear expectations, which significantly helps employees. When people understand their role, they can accomplish work-related goals and understand daily expectations. This helps employers and upper management to keep track of job site progress. Furthermore, avoiding unnecessary injuries is another reason why communication is important in the oil and gas industry. The oil and gas industry has a high fatality and injury rate on its own, so taking steps to avoid mishaps is vital! Communication and productivity go hand in hand, especially in the oil and gas industry. Without instructions, workers cannot complete projects. In addition, they may shy away from taking initiative because they might be unsure about procedures. Luckily, employers can provide instructions and answer questions about various topics. Doing so will keep everyone on track as they efficiently work on tasks (Bogg, 2022). Workers will nurture a greater sense of personal understanding of how each of them is affecting their teammates and develop their own ideal style for better communication skills to achieve higher levels of personal and organizational leadership, motivation and focus in achieving common Objectives. Workers will walk away with more courage and insights to create a more passionate and fulfilled work environment and the skills to not only greater strengths in communication to move others to higher levels of excellence, but a greater ability to lead and inspire motivated teams with more personal and organizational achievement and success (Directive Communication International, 2020).

Business

A *business* is defined as an organization or enterprising entity engaged in commercial, industrial, or professional activities. A business can be described as an organization or enterprising entity that engages in professional, commercial or industrial activities. There can be different types of businesses depending on various factors. Some are for-profit, while some are non-profit. Similarly, their ownership also makes them different from each other. For instance, there are sole proprietorships, partnerships, corporations, and more. Business is also the efforts and activities of a person who is producing goods or offering services with the intent to sell them for profit. Business refers to an enterprising entity or organization that carries out professional activities. They can be commercial, industrial, or others. For-profit business entities do business to earn a profit, while non-profit ones do it for a

charitable mission. Business ownership includes partnerships, sole proprietorships, corporations, etc. Businesses can be small-scale or large-scale. (The Economic Times, 2023). Business is the practice of making one's living or making money by producing or buying and selling products (such as goods and services, (*American Heritage Dictionary 2019*). It is also "any activity or enterprise entered into for profit (*Burton William, 2007*).

Transformation

It refers to the act, process, or instance of transforming or being transformed. Regarding transformative learning, Mezirow indicates learning occurs when there is a transformation in one of our beliefs or attitudes, or a change of our entire perspective. A process of change and development. When it refers to human transformation, it implies an internal change and growth to one's highest potential or best oneself, which affects one's worldview, behaviors, and thought.

Business Transformation

Business transformation is an umbrella term for making fundamental changes in how a business or organization runs. This includes personnel, processes, and technology. These transformations help organizations compete more effectively, become more efficient, or make a wholesale strategic pivot. Business transformation is a term used to describe what happens when a company makes fundamental changes to how it operates, typically with the aim of enhancing both operational and financial performance. A business transformation initiative could apply to the organization as a whole or a part of it, such as a department or product line (Lawton, 2022). No business can stand the test of time without adapting to change, and business transformation is the act of rolling out strategic growth or change plans across an organization. These changes tend to be significant, not simple tweaks to process. Digital business transformation can impact business processes like the business model, business ecosystem, business asset management, organizational culture, partnership models and customer approaches (Airfocus, 2022).

Components of Business Transformation that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Mogg (2022) enumerated the following as components of Business transformation: Improving customer experience, business culture, operating models, and other aspects. All aim to improve how business is conducted across business models. Panorama (2022) enumerated the following as components of business transformation: Maximizing efficiency, ensuring safety, increasing sustainability, optimizing organizational efficiency, Improving the customer experience and Increasing employee experience.

Customer Experience

Today, businesses seek to offer quality customer service by interacting with them through multiple channels. Gas and oil companies also have a peculiar opportunity to get this trend, providing millions of data points with deep insights that provide a better-quality experience. At this point, gas and oil firms can easily make this digital transition with the help of analytical platforms (Dataroid, 2022). Refining the customer experience has become a vital focus across various organizations, from retail to technology to banking. It has become clear that the retail industry and, for that matter, the fuel and convenience industry take a serious look at how it wants to engage, interact and transact with its customers or risk losing market share. The overall fuel and convenience-retail industry has put in more effort in recent years to provide a reliable and personalized consumer experience as a result of legacy processes and IT, in addition to a rapidly evolving payments landscape indoor and now outdoor (Seemann, 2018).

Employee Experience

The employee experience is the interactions or the level of activities employee has with people, systems, policies, and the physical and virtual workspace. Both the small activities details of day-to-day work and the periodic events and transitions matter. It is the holistic impact of the job and the organization on the individual how employees feel, perceive their potential and abilities, and the effect on their well-being (Miles, 2023). With unprecedented changes to our society, economy, and businesses, how employees experience work has become more important. It is believed the employee experience and its relationship with engagement and performance is critical to understand and prioritize – now more than ever (Lee, 2023). Employee experience encapsulates what people encounter and observe over the course of their tenure at an organization. Companies often focus extensively on the customer experience both in terms of processes and service level. With today's competitive market for top talent,

organizations must increasingly focus on delivering a positive employee experience to attract, hire and retain skilled workers. Companies always focus widely on the customer experience both in terms of processes and service level. With today's competitive market for top talent, organizations must increasingly focus on delivering a positive employee experience to attract, hire and retain skilled workers. Due to the ever-present need to retain the best talent, most employers provide detailed training plans for their workers as part of their role (Taylor 2022).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Technology acceptance model (TAM) by (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1990). The study was anchored on technology acceptance theory (TAM) as it postulates that attitude and subjective norms influence behavioral intention. Theory of reason of action was proceeds from a study on the adoption and behavior that originates from computer and technology. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) originated from the Theory of Reason Action (TRA) (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1990) which states that attitude and subjective norms influence behavioral intention. The TRA was proceeds from a study on the adoption and behaviour that originates from computer technology (Raharja, Tresna & Rivani, 2019). The application of TRA by Davis (1989) resulted to TAM: The most acceptable and recognized behavioral theory of technology adoption. According to Dahnil, Marzuki, Langgat, and Noor (2014) the two key constructs that influences intention to use a technology are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. TAM as introduced by Davis (1989) suggests that perceived usefulness is derived by potential users who use a particular system that will change its actions, and perceived ease of use is the expectation of users about the difficulty or ease of using the target system

Empirical Review

The Relationship Between E-Safety and Customer Experience

Efeeloo (2017) conducted a study on the influence of safety practices on performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study specifically looked at the influence of Regular Provision/use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Daily Safety Briefings on the profitability of Oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Data were obtained by means of questionnaire. Analyses were performed using Pearson's product moment coefficient of correlation and regression analyses via the use of SPSS. The findings reveal a statistically positive correlation between safety practices and the performance of oil and gas companies. Further, safety practices positively influence the Operating Profit Margin (OPROM) and Return on Turnover (ROTUN) of the companies. The study recommended that continuous safety practices by all oil and gas firms to enable them to have smooth performance and enhanced profitability.

Ambituuni, Amezaga, and Emeseh (2018) conducted a study on the Analysis of safety and environmental regulations for downstream petroleum industry operations in Nigeria: problems and prospects. The Nigerian economy depends on the petroleum industry for revenue and fuel to drive its growth. However, the petroleum industry has been associated with major issues of accidents and disasters which have contributed to vast safety and environmental problems. This is especially true for all sectors of the industry including the downstream. Against this back-drop, this paper critically examines the provisions in various environmental and petroleum laws and the institutional arrangements for monitoring and enforcement to evaluate their adequacy for ensuring safety and proper environmental management within the downstream sector. The review revealed the limitations of the framework such as incoherent laws, overlaps, duplications and conflicting regulatory functions.

Victor (2020) conducted a study on Health and Safety Training and Employee Performance in Oil and Gas Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between health and safety training and employee performance in oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. Primary data was generated through structured questionnaire based on the 5-point Likert scale. The population of the study was 250 employees of seven (7) selected oil and gas servicing companies in Rivers State. The sample size of 154 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0. The tests were carried out at a 95% confidence interval and at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between health and safety training and employee performance in oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Pham and Yazdani (2021) conducted a study on the mediating role of customer experience on the relationship between online shopping determinants such as: payment barrier, bad complaint resolve, slow delivery process, poor product quality, technical problem, and customer satisfaction in Vietnam. The online survey is conducted according to the related theories, relevant empirical evidence, and pilot study to collect reliable data from 360-400 respondents in Ho Chi Minh city and Ha Noi city. Some quantitative data analysis techniques are proposed and used in this study, including descriptive statistics, reliability, explanatory factor analysis, variance analysis, Pearson correlation analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and structural equation modeling. For using them, the researcher expects that all factors have significant and negative effect on customer satisfaction through customer experience. By developing one of the first research attempt on pre-normal phase of COVID-19 pandemic, the researchers believe the marketers and top managers at e-commerce companies in Vietnam to have sufficient information about how their customers' experience with online shopping platforms and related services

Bestman and Amabo (2022) conducted a study on Knowledge Application and Organizational Sustainability of Oil and Gas Companies in Rivers State. This study examined the relationship between knowledge application and organizational sustainability of oil and gas companies in Rivers State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey in its investigation of the variables. Primary data was generated through structured administered questionnaire. The population for this study was is made up of the twenty-four registered indigenous oil servicing companies in Port Harcourt. Since the population is small, this study therefore adopts the entire population of 24 oil and gas companies in Rivers State as a census. Five (5) managers were selected from each of 24 oil and gas companies in Rivers State giving a total of 120 respondents. The tests were carried out at a 0.05 significance level. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman rank order correlation Coefficient. The tests were carried out at a 95% confidence interval and a 0.05 level of significance. The study findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between enterprise knowledge audit and organizational sustainability of oil and gas companies in Rivers State.

The Relationship Between Communication and Employee Experience

Dehghan & Ma'toufi (2016) conducted a study on the relationship between communication skills and organizational commitment to employees' job performance in Golestan's National Company distribution of petroleum products. So, the present study in terms of purpose is applied research and considering the time dimension is retrospective and in regard to its results is results-oriented. Also, this research in terms of data collection is descriptive and between descriptive research methods is survey research that its most important advantage is the generalization capability of obtained results. Due to the different divisions in the survey research in terms of checked accuracy the present study is cross-sectional study, the statistical population of this research is Petroleum Products National Company of distribution Employees from Golestan who are 260 people, Simple random sampling method based on Cochran method were selected 155 peoples as samples. To analyze the data, descriptive statistic and inferential statistics (normality test, Pearson correlation, and Watson, f-test and regression analysis) were used. The results showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between communication skills and organizational commitment to employees' job performance

Olusegun (2018) conducted a study on Employee Voice: Speaking up in Organization as a Correlate of Employee Productivity in Oil and Gas Industry - an Empirical Investigation from Nigeria. The understanding and interpretation of voice have been given critical attention among researchers, practitioners in recent years. The firm believes of the workforce that they can openly express their personal opinion and concerns to higher authority in the organization, and who believe that they can influence the decision, are likely to demonstrate optimistic attitude and constructive behaviour. The study surveyed 1067 employees of Nigerian oil and gas and 902 respondents were returned and

used for the study. Data were obtained from the participants using a questionnaire of 19 question items by means of probability sampling strategy, while the research design was cross-sectional. The findings of the study indicate a coherent and consistent one with literature. The study employed eight dimensions as drivers of employee voice in the Nigeria oil and gas industry which discovered mixed outcomes. One of the drivers is the communication/exchange of views which had an inverse association with employee productivity. Employee collective representation and employee engagement also recorded an insignificant relationship with employee productive work behaviour.

Omoankhanlen (2021) conducted a study on Employee Wellbeing and Organizational Effectiveness of Oil and Gas Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study deals with the nexus amongst employee wellbeing and organizational effectiveness of oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The cross-sectional survey was adopted. A total population of six hundred and sixty-five (665) employees from 10 oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, was covered in this work. A sample size of 250 was drawn from the population. The simple random sampling technique was employed. The questionnaire was used to obtain the necessary data from respondents. The spearman rank-order correlation was used for analyzing the data. The result revealed that the dimensions of employee wellbeing (job satisfaction, and work-life balance satisfaction) had a significant positive relationship with cohesion and productivity. It was thus concluded that enhancing the total wellbeing of the employees by ensuring job satisfaction and work-life balance satisfaction of the employees, will help enhance the total effectiveness of the organization.

Asikhia, Makinde, Akinlabi & Ajani (2022) conducted a study on the Effect of Employee Mobility on Skills Retention in Upstream Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria. This paper investigated effect of employee mobility on skills retention in upstream oil and gas companies in Nigeria. A review of pertinent conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature was done and a hypothesis was formulated. Three upstream oil and gas companies were surveyed using proportionate and stratified random sampling techniques. A total population of 9,437 regular and contract employees were investigated with a sample size of 807. The validity of the instrument was determined using content and construct validity while Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Multiple linear regression Analysis was used to analyze the hypothesis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (V26.0). The study found that employee mobility components have positive and significant effect on skills retention of selected upstream oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Findings further revealed that employee buy-in has the highest contribution to skills retention in the selected upstream oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Allen (2022) conducted a study on Philosophy of Privacy and Digital Life. The emergence of digital life has created conceptual and ethical problems of a sort I believe academic philosophers are well suited to address. One of the most widely acknowledged and debated sets of questions and concerns generated by digital life relates to privacy or, more broadly, to data protection. These persistent and internationally acknowledged issues explain the new subfield within academic philosophy that is now emergent both in Europe and North America, which I will dub the "Philosophy of Privacy." Our subfield most of my books fall within it has produced sole-authored books by several philosophers, several anthologies, and many papers on specific topics. But something is missing. Comprehensive philosophies of privacy and data protection are missing and scarcely attempted. Privacy theorists abound who are narrowly focused on ways to conceptualize privacy or data protection that they believe will facilitate better business practices or legal regulations. The philosophy of privacy is a project of greater magnitude, more comprehensive, and cumulative. The most comprehensive philosophy of privacy and data protection, which I will call "the philosophy of privacy" for short, would include a descriptive and prescriptive theory of privacy's associated meanings, values, politics, and purposes, including an account of how we might live digitally driven and digitally reliant lives well, in a world that may or may not confer all of the opportunities for privacy, private choice, and data security ideal theories would commend.

Gap in Empirical Review

The few studies done were carried outside Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the e-safety and customer experience; effective communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Simple linear regression and Z test while the present study made use of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The area of the study was River's state, Nigeria. The population of the study were five (5) Oil firms in Rivers, with three thousand three hundred and eighty-six (3,386) selected staff from the selected Oil firms in Rivers State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The adequate sample size of 345, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 295 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 86 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.84 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistics tool.

Data Presentation, Analyses and Interpretation

Distribution and returned Questionnaire

The chapter presents and analyzes the data collected for the study. The presentation and interpretation of data were based on the questionnaire administrated to the staff of the Oil firms under study. Table 1 shows the Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire from the Universities.

Table 1: Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

Firms	Distributed	No Returned	percent	No not Returned	Percent
1. Shell Petroleum Dev. Comp Ltd	83	76	22	7	2
2. Belema Oil Producing Ltd	63	50	14	13	4
3. Chevron Texaco Ltd	52	50	14	2	1
4. Dominos oil and Gas services	77	67	20	10	3
5. Masters Energy Oil and Gas Ltd	70	52	15	18	5
Total	345	295	84	50	16

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Three hundred and forty-five (345) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and two hundred and ninety-five (295) copies were returned representing eighty-four (84) percent, while fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing sixteen (16) percent. That showed a high rate of response.

Relationship Between E-Safety and Customer Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 2: Responses to research question one on the relationship between e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	$\sum FX$	- X	SD	Decision
1	E-safety allows customers to have a positive experience when interacting with a company online	495 99 33.6	320 80 27.1	96 32 10.8	64 32 10.8	52 52 17.6	1027 295 100%	3.48.	1.484	Agree
2	A positive customer experience lead to repeat customers and positive word-of-mouth for the company	375 75 25.4	320 80 27.1	120 40 13.6	64 32 10.8	68 68 23.1	947 295 100%	3.21	1.511	Agree
3	E-safety has positive influence on customer repurchase intention	415 83 28.1	352 88 29.8	156 52 17.6	40 20 6.8	52 52 17.6	1015 295 100%	3.44	1.417	Agree
4	Online search for the company products to understand its	475 95 32.2	352 88 29.8	84 28 9.5	120 60 20.3	24 24 8.1	1055 295 100%	3.58	1.338	Agree

	features are enhanced through e-safety									
5	Browsing through the online marketplace for reviews and customer support are promoted with the help of e-safety	415	352	156	88	28	1039	3.52	1.298	Agree
		83	88	52	44	28	295			
		28.1	29.8	17.6	14.9	9.5	100%			
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.446	1.4096	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 179 respondents out of 295 representing 60.7 percent agreed that E-safety allows customers to have a positive experience when interacting with a company online with mean score 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.484. A positive customer experience led to repeat customers and positive word-of-mouth for the company 155 respondents representing 52.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.21 and a standard deviation of 1.511. E-safety has positive influence on customer repurchase intention 171 respondents representing 57.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.44 and standard deviation of 1.417. Online search for the company products to understand its features are enhanced through e-safety 183 respondents representing 62.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.58 and 1.338. Browsing through the online marketplace for reviews and customer support are promoted with the help of e-safety 171. respondents representing 57.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 1.298.

Relationship Between Communication and Employee Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 3: Responses to research question one on the relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	$\sum FX$	- X	SD	Decision
1	Flow of communication in the company reduces turnover	355	560	84	88	12	1099	3.73	1.108	Agree
		71	140	28	44	12	295			
		24.1	47.5	9.5	14.9	4.1	100%			
2	Employee learn about important news from an Internal source	315	560	12	96	40	1023	3.47	1.350	Agree
		63	140	4	48	40	295			
		21.4	47.5	1.4	16.3	13.6	100%			
3	The more satisfied and appreciated a company's employee are, the more likely they are to work harder	315	576	74	112	8	1085		1.093	Agree
		63	144	24	56	8	295	3.67		
		21.4	48.8	8.1	19.0	2.7	100%			
4	Technological makes the day easier as employees need to do their work through telephones and computers	295	464	180	96	12	1047	3.39	1.365	Agree
		59	116	60	48	12	295			
		21.4	48.8	8.1	16.3	4.0	100%			
5	Reaching goals together increases the feeling of teamwork and progress in the company	495	320	168	104	8	1095	3.71	1.182	Agree
		99	80	56	52	8	295			
		33.6	27.1	19.0	17.6	2.7	100%			
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.594	1.2196	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3, 211 respondents out of 295 representing 71.6 percent agreed that flow of communication in the company reduces turnover with mean score 3.73 and a standard deviation of 1.108. Employee learn about important news from an Internal source 203 respondents representing 68.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 1.350. The more satisfied and appreciated a company's employee are, the more likely they are to work harder 207 respondents representing 70.3 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.67 and standard deviation of

1.039. Technological makes the day easier as employees need to do their work through telephones and computers 175 respondents representing 70.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.93 and 1.365. Reaching goals together increases the feeling of teamwork and progress in the company 179 respondents representing 60.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 1.182.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 4: Contingency table of the Relationship E-Safety and Customer Experience of Gasoline Firms

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
1.	E-safety allows customers to have a positive experience when interacting with a company online	71	140	28	44	12	295
2.	A positive customer experience led to repeat customers and positive word-of-mouth for the company	63	140	4	48	40	295
3.	E-safety has positive influence on customer repurchase intention	63	144	24	56	8	295
4.	Online search for the company products to understand its features are enhanced through e-safety	59	116	60	48	12	295
5.	Browsing through the online marketplace for reviews and customer support are promoted with the help of e-safety	99	80	56	52	8	295
	Total	355	620	172	248	80	1475

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 Shows the correlation of there is no significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 5: Correlations Between E-Safety and Customer Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Correlations						
		E-safety allows customers to have a positive experience when interacting with a company online	A positive customer experience led to repeat customers and positive word-of-mouth for the company	E-safety has positive influence on customer repurchase intention	Online search for the company products to understand its features are enhanced through e-safety	Browsing through the online marketplace for reviews and customer support are promoted with the help of e-safety
E-safety allows customers to have a positive experience when interacting with a company online	Pearson Correlation	1	.677**	.662**	.710**	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
A positive customer experience led to repeat customers and positive	Pearson Correlation	.677**	1	.624**	.452**	.610**

word-of-mouth for the company	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
E-safety has positive influence on customer repurchase intention	Pearson Correlation	.662**	.624**	1	.798**	.983**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
Online search for the company products to understand its features are enhanced through e-safety	Pearson Correlation	.710**	.452**	.798**	1	.782**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
Browsing through the online marketplace for reviews and customer support are promoted with the help of e-safety	Pearson Correlation	.632**	.610**	.983**	.782**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	295	295	295	295	295

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5, Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .610 < .983. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria ($r = .588 < .983$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .610 < .983, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .610 < .983$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .610 < .983, p < .05$).

Hypothesis Two: There is no significance relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 6 shows contingency table of the relationship communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 6: Contingency Table of the Relationship Communication and Employee Experience of Gasoline Firms

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
1.	Flow of communication in the company reduces turnover	71	140	28	44	12	295
2.	Employee learn about important news from an Internal source	63	140	4	48	40	295
3.	The more satisfied and appreciated a company's employee are, the more likely they are to work harder	63	144	24	56	8	295
4.	Technological makes the day easier as employees need to do their work through telephones and computers	59	116	60	48	12	295
5.	Reaching goals together increases the feeling of teamwork and progress in the company	99	80	56	52	8	295
	Total	355	1,220	172	248	80	1,475

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 7 Shows the Correlation of there is no Significance Positive Relationship Communication and Employee Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 7: Correlations Between Communication and Employee Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

		Correlations				
		Follow of communication in the company reduces turnover	Employee learn about important news from an Internal source	The more satisfied and appreciated a company's employee are, the more likely they are to work harder	Technological makes the day easier as employees need to do their work through telephones and computers	Reaching goals together increases the feeling of teamwork and progress in the company
Follow of communication in the company reduces turnover	Pearson Correlation	1	.846**	.844**	.480**	.664**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
Employee learn about important news from an Internal source	Pearson Correlation	.846**	1	.967**	.640**	.584**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
The more satisfied and appreciated a company's employee are, the more likely they are to work harder	Pearson Correlation	.844**	.967**	1	.592**	.598**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295

Technological makes the day easier as employees need to do their work through telephones and computers	Pearson Correlation	.480**	.640**	.592**	1	.411**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	295	295	295	295	295
Reaching goals together increases the feeling of teamwork and progress in the company	Pearson Correlation	.664**	.584**	.598**	.411**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	295	295	295	295	295
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 7 shows the Pearson correlation matrix on communication and employee experience showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .411 <.846. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was significance relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria ($r=.411 <.846$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .411 <.846, p<.05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .411 <.846$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was significance positive relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r=.411 <.846, p<.05$).

Discussions of Findings

The Relationship Between E-Safety and Customer Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria

From the result of the hypothesis one, the computed ($r = .610 <.983$) is greater than the table value of .000. Therefore, we concluded that there was significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .610 <.983, p<.05$). In the support of the literature review, Efeeloo (2017) conducted a study on the influence of safety practices on performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The findings reveal a statistically positive correlation between safety practices and the performance of oil and gas companies. Further, safety practices positively influence the Operating Profit Margin (OPROM) and Return on Turnover (ROTUN) of the companies. The study recommended that continuous safety practices by all oil and gas firms to enable them to have smooth performance and enhanced profitability. Ambituuni, Amezaga, and Emeseh (2018), conducted a study on the Analysis of safety and environmental regulations for downstream petroleum industry operations in Nigeria: problems and prospects. The review revealed the limitations of the framework such as incoherent laws, overlaps, duplications and conflicting regulatory functions. However, the paper did find that provisions in the Petroleum Industry Bill (PIB) (Draft) and National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA) Amendment Bill offers some prospects that address some of the limitations within the reviewed framework. Victor (2020), conducted a study on Health and Safety Training and Employee Performance in Oil and Gas Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between health and safety training and employee performance in oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The Relationship Between Communication and Employee Experience of Gasoline Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

From the result of the hypothesis two, the computed ($r = .411 < .846$) is greater than the table value of .000. Therefore, we concluded that there was significance positive relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .411 < .846, p < .05$). In the support of the literature review, Allen (2022), conducted a study on Philosophy of Privacy and Digital Life. The most comprehensive philosophy of privacy would engage the insights of computer and information sciences, and other academic disciplines, such as psychology, sociology, economics, and law, where theories of privacy have been advanced since the 1970s. I describe the parameters of a comprehensive philosophy of privacy. Asikhia, Makinde, Akinlabi, and Ajani (2022), conducted a study on the Effect of Employee Mobility on Skills Retention in Upstream Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria. The study found that employee mobility components have positive and significant effect on skills retention of selected upstream oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

- i. There was significance positive relationship e-safety and customer experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, $r(95, n = 295) = .610 < .983, p < .05$
- ii. There was significance positive relationship between communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, $r(95, n = 295) = .411 < .846, p < .05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that e-safety and communication had positive significant relationship with customer experience and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Now more than ever, we recognize the power of digital technology to transcend geographical and information gaps and help countries and institutions work together, be it during natural disasters or in daily life. Together, we can leverage technology to build a better society for the future." Digital transformation is a journey with multiple connected intermediary goals, in the end, striving towards ubiquitous optimization across processes, divisions and the business ecosystem of a hyper-connected age were building the right bridges (between front end and back office, data from 'things and decisions, people, teams, technologies, various players in ecosystems etc.) in function of that journey is key to succeed.

Recommendations

Based on the Findings the Following Recommendations Were Made:

- i. The management of the gasoline firms should endeavor to be safe online to protect individuals themselves and others from online harms and risks which may jeopardize their personal information, lead to unsafe communications or even effect their mental health and wellbeing.
- ii. *It is necessary to have Effective communication that will create mutual understanding and trust among the members of the organization.* It promotes co-operation between the employer and the workers

Contribution to Knowledge

The few studies done were carried outside Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the e-safety and customer experience; effective communication and employee experience of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Simple linear regression and Z test while the present study made use of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study filled the research gap by evaluating the Digital life and business transformation of Gasoline firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

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